

Enabling technologies in the Marche Region

This research is carried out by the University of Macerata with the aim of studying the use of enabling technologies in companies in the Marche Region and identifying the most appropriate interventions for their diffusion in the territory.

The research takes place in the context of the TRUST project, a European Horizon 2020 – MSCA – RISE project which aims to understand the role of trust in the implementation of digital technologies and suggest real development measures. For more information, visit the project website <https://trust-rise.eu/>

Respondents are informed that:

- The questionnaire is anonymous, i.e. no personal data is collected.
- The data collected will be presented in an aggregated manner.
- The collected data will be used exclusively for research purposes.

For further information and clarifications, please contact Niccolò Testi, PhD student at the University of Macerata, at n.testi@unimc.it

*Campo obbligatorio

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Declaration of Consent

If you wish to continue with the questionnaire, please tick the following box.

1. *

Seleziona tutte le voci applicabili.

I have read and understood the above information and agree to participate in this research

About the company

2. Size *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- Micro (less than 10 employees)
- Small (less than 50 employees)
- Medium (less than 250 employees)
- Large (more than 250 employees)

3. ATECO 2007 Classification *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- A - AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING
- B - EXTRACTION OF MINERALS FROM QUARRIES AND MINES
- C - MANUFACTURING ACTIVITIES
- D - SUPPLY OF ELECTRICITY, GAS, STEAM AND AIR CONDITIONING
- E - WATER SUPPLY; SEWERAGE, WASTE MANAGEMENT AND REMEDIATION ACTIVITIES
- F - CONSTRUCTION
- G - WHOLESALE AND RETAIL TRADE; REPAIR OF MOTOR VEHICLES AND MOTORCYCLES
- H - TRANSPORTATION AND STORAGE
- I - ACCOMMODATION AND CATERING SERVICE ACTIVITIES
- J - INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES
- K - FINANCIAL AND INSURANCE ACTIVITIES
- L - REAL ESTATE ACTIVITIES
- M - PROFESSIONAL, SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL ACTIVITIES
- N - RENTAL, TRAVEL AGENCIES, BUSINESS SUPPORT SERVICES
- O - PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION AND DEFENSE; COMPULSORY SOCIAL INSURANCE
- P - EDUCATION
- Q - HEALTH AND SOCIAL ASSISTANCE
- R - ARTISTIC, SPORTS, ENTERTAINMENT AND FUN ACTIVITIES
- S - OTHER SERVICE ACTIVITIES
- T - ACTIVITIES OF FAMILIES AND COHABITANTS AS EMPLOYERS FOR DOMESTIC PERSONNEL; PRODUCTION OF UNDIFFERENTIATED GOODS AND SERVICES FOR OWN USE BY FAMILIES AND COHABITANTS
- U - EXTRATERRITORIAL ORGANIZATIONS AND BODIES
- Altro: _____

4. What is the main economic activity of the company? *

5. Is the company an innovative startup or innovative SME? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

Yes

No

Altro: _____

The enabling technologies within the company

6. Which of the following Industry 4.0 enabling technologies are used in the company? *

Seleziona tutte le voci applicabili.

- Collaborative robots interconnected and quickly programmable
- 3D printers connected to digital development software
- Augmented reality to support production processes
- Simulations between interconnected machines to optimize processes
- Integration and exchange of information horizontally and vertically along the value chain from supplier to consumer
- Industrial internet: communication between elements of production, not only within the company, but also externally, thanks to the use of the internet
- Cloud: the online storage of information, the use of cloud computing, external data analysis services, etc.
- Cyber-security
- Big Data and Analytics: techniques for managing very large amounts of data through open systems that allow forecasts or predictions
- None of the above

7. Recently, blockchain technology has established itself among the enabling technologies of Industry 4.0. Your company: *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- does not know the blockchain technology *Passa alla domanda 12.*
- is aware of blockchain technology but has not yet explored its potential use in the company *Passa alla domanda 12.*
- looked into the potential use of blockchain technology for the company and decided not to use it *Passa alla domanda 8.*
- is working concretely to start using blockchain technology *Passa alla domanda 9.*
- already uses blockchain technology *Passa alla domanda 10.*
- offers companies services based on blockchain or distributed ledger technology *Passa alla domanda 11.*
- Altro: _____

8. Can you tell us more about the reasons that led the company to decide not to use blockchain technology?

Passa alla domanda 12.

9. Can you explain what use the company plans to make of blockchain technology?

Passa alla domanda 12.

10. Can you explain what use the company is making of blockchain technology?

Passa alla domanda 12.

11. Can you explain what kind of services related to blockchain or distributed ledger technology does the company offer?

Passa alla domanda 12.

Collaborations with public and private actors

12. With which players does the company regularly collaborate in the exploration/design/implementation of enabling technologies?
(multiple cells can be selected for each row)

Seleziona tutte le voci applicabili.

	nella Regione Marche	in altre Regioni Italiane	all'estero
Universities and/or research centres	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Enterprise Clusters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Government institutions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Digital Innovation Hubs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Trade Associations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Companies that use enabling technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Companies that provide enabling technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

13. Does the company collaborate with other public and private actors not included in the previous list? If yes, which ones?

Measures for the dissemination of enabling technologies

14. In your opinion, how useful would the following measures be to spread the use * of enabling technologies of Industry 4.0 in companies in the Marche Region?

Contrassegna solo un ovale per riga.

	I don't know	Not at all	Not much	Quite	Very much
More funding	<input type="radio"/>				
Awareness raising activities	<input type="radio"/>				
Training activities	<input type="radio"/>				
Networking activities with companies that use Industry 4.0 technologies	<input type="radio"/>				
Networking activities with universities/research centres	<input type="radio"/>				
Clear laws governing the business uses of blockchain technology	<input type="radio"/>				

15. In your opinion, what other measures could be useful?

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